

Alpine butterflies want to fly high: Species and communities shift upwards faster than their host plants (*in: Ecology*)

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Figures S1: Figures required for the script analyzing butterfly and host plant richness patterns, drivers of butterfly richness and drivers of change in butterfly richness, as well as calculating butterfly community shifts and individual shifts of butterfly and host plant species in the national park Berchtesgaden, Bavarian Alps, Germany. The Markdown file and the data required to run the script are hosted separately on Dryad.

File descriptions (Kerner_et_al-2022-FiguresS1.zip)

`climate_stations_temperature.jpeg` – example of temperature modelling for each plot (= Figure S1). The figure was created externally and saved here for importation into the script.

`location_study_sites_and_climate_stations.png` – location of study sites and climate stations, including changes in temperatures between years. The figure was created externally after exporting the temperature graph from R and saved here for importation into the script.

`Logo_ (...).png` – all five files beginning with “Logo_” contain the externally created icons used in the figures.

All final figures of the manuscript are included in the Markdown file when running the code and are also exported into a Word file when clicking 'knit' in the RStudio pane showing the code. Therefore, figures are not additionally saved in the figure folder, although some will be cached there for later reimportation into the script when running the code.